

Attention-Enhanced ResNet50 for Robust Multi-Class Classification of Intraocular Tumors in Ultra-Widefield Fundus Images

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Abstract

Accurate multi-class classification of intraocular tumors remains a challenging task due to subtle inter-class variations, limited annotated datasets, and the complexity of ultra-widefield (UWF) fundus imaging. This study proposes an attention-enhanced deep learning framework based on ResNet-50 for robust classification of six categories of intraocular conditions using the UWF Fundus Images of Intraocular Tumors dataset (2,031 images). Transfer learning was employed to leverage pretrained hierarchical representations, and systematic ablation experiments were conducted to evaluate the impact of input resolution, Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) attention placement, and layer freezing strategies. Results demonstrated that an input resolution of 768×768 pixels provided an optimal balance between preserving fine pathological details and computational efficiency. Selective integration of SE attention in the deepest residual stage significantly improved generalization performance (Test Accuracy = 0.985, F1-score = 0.986, Cohen's Kappa = 0.972), outperforming the baseline ResNet-50. In contrast, distributing attention across multiple stages increased model complexity without consistent gains in robustness. Furthermore, strategic freezing of early residual layers functioned as an effective regularization mechanism, enhancing generalization under limited data conditions. The findings indicate that careful optimization of attention depth and parameter adaptation is critical for achieving stable and clinically reliable multi-class intraocular tumor classification.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Deep learning, Tumor Classification, Intraocular Tumors, ResNet50

1. Introduction

Intraocular tumors refer to abnormal cellular growths that develop within the eye. These tumors may arise primarily from ocular tissues (such as retina, choroid, etc.) or occur secondarily due to metastatic spread from other malignant tumors. Intraocular tumors may be

classified according to a wide range of variables, including their malignant potential, incidence, age of presentation, anatomical location within the eye, tissue from which the tumor arises, and relation to systemic disease [1]. Benign tumors include Choroidal Hemangioma (CH), Retinal Capillary Hemangioma (RCH), Choroidal Osteoma (CO), et cetera, while malignant tumors encompass Retinoblastoma (RB), Uveal Melanoma (UM), and intraocular metastases. Both benign and malignant tumors can cause visual impairment, with malignant tumors posing a substantial risk of mortality due to their potential for local invasion and metastasis [2]. Uveal melanoma is the most common malignant primary intraocular tumor in adults, and Retinoblastoma is the most common malignant primary intraocular tumor in children [3].

Figure 1: Uveal melanoma in the choroid [1]

Patients with intraocular tumors may present with acute vision-related symptoms, such as reduced visual acuity, visual field defects, flashing lights or floaters; however, they can be asymptomatic, depending on the size and location of the tumor. A significant number of asymptomatic patients harboring an intraocular tumor are diagnosed on routine eye examinations or as part of screening surveys for other diseases such as diabetic retinopathy [1].

Intraocular malignant tumors are rare but often seriously affect vision and may threaten life because of their location and growth characteristics. Therefore, timely diagnosis and treatment of these tumors are of critical importance [4]. Fundus photography is a non-invasive, cost-

effective imaging method commonly used for screening, diagnosing, and monitoring retinal and intraocular pathologies [2].

Traditionally, the diagnosis of ocular tumors has relied heavily on the manual evaluation of fundus images by ophthalmologists, a process that, while thorough, is time-consuming and subject to human error and variability between clinicians. These limitations underscore the critical need for automated, efficient, and accurate diagnostic tools that can reduce workload and improve diagnostic consistency. The integration of Deep Learning (DL) and advanced image processing techniques into medical diagnostics presents a transformative opportunity to address these challenges, particularly in ophthalmology, where visual data plays a central role in disease identification [5], [6].

Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have shown great promise in automating the screening and diagnosis of fundus diseases, including diabetic retinopathy, age-related macular degeneration, and glaucoma [7], [8], [9]. Despite recent advances in DL for ophthalmic image analysis, automated classification of intraocular tumors remains challenging. Existing studies have often focused on single-tumor detection or limited-class scenarios, with insufficient attention to multi-class discrimination using ultra-wide-field fundus images [10], [11], [12].

Moreover, variations in tumor morphology, subtle inter-class differences, and limited annotated datasets hinder robust generalization of conventional convolutional architectures. These challenges highlight the need for optimized DL frameworks capable of capturing fine-grained tumor-specific features while maintaining stability and clinical reliability [2].

In this study, we propose an attention-enhanced DL framework for automated multi-class classification of intraocular tumors using ultra-wide-field fundus images. Built upon the ResNet-50 backbone and optimized via transfer learning, the model leverages pretrained hierarchical representations while adapting high-level features to tumor-specific patterns. Channel-wise feature refinement is incorporated to strengthen discriminative capacity and improve generalization. The proposed approach is designed to function as a computer-aided diagnosis tool, facilitating accurate and efficient intraocular tumor assessment.

2. Literature Review

Recent advances in deep DL have significantly transformed medical image analysis by enabling high-precision, scalable, and efficient diagnostic frameworks. Ophthalmology, in particular, represents a domain well-suited for DL integration due to its strong dependence on image-based evaluation for disease detection and monitoring. DL models have demonstrated the capacity to analyze complex ophthalmic imaging modalities, including fundus photography, optical coherence tomography (OCT), and slit-lamp imaging by extracting high-dimensional feature representations and identifying subtle pathological patterns. Numerous studies have reported performance comparable to, and in certain tasks exceeding, that of expert clinicians in the detection of diabetic retinopathy, age-related macular degeneration, and glaucoma [13].

Several recent studies have explored DL for ocular tumor detection and classification; however, many have focused on external ocular tumour and eyelid tumors rather than

intraocular lesions [14], [15], [16]. While these approaches highlight the potential of AI in oncologic ophthalmology, their scope differs substantially from intraocular tumor analysis, where imaging characteristics, anatomical context, and diagnostic complexity are markedly distinct. One of the primary challenges in this domain is the lack of annotated, accurate, and available datasets, which restricts the development and validation of robust classification models.

Several studies have explored the application of DL techniques in ocular oncology; most investigations have focused on individual tumor entities, particularly retinoblastoma or uveal melanoma, or have addressed narrowly defined classification scenarios like binary classification [11], [17], [18], [19].

Most research conducted on the performance of DL in ocular oncology has highlighted the efficacy of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) In particular ResNet50 and transfer learning in ophthalmic oncology [11], [16], [20], [21]. Initial studies demonstrated that CNNs could leverage color and structural information in fundus images to achieve meaningful diagnostic performance. For instance, a color-fusion CNN applied to 798 ultra-widefield (UWF) fundus images for distinguishing uveal melanoma from choroidal nevi achieved an accuracy of 89.72% and F1-score of 0.8492 by applying Intermediate Fusion, underscoring the influence of color features on model performance [19]. Similarly, an approach combining OpenCV-based feature extraction with CNN classification for intraocular retinoblastoma (iRB) on 771 fundus images reported classification accuracy of 74.2% on the test set [18].

Subsequent work leveraged deeper architectures such as ResNet-50 for retinoblastoma classification, employing a dataset of 36,623 fundus images to categorize normal, stable, and active disease. This model achieved 99% accuracy in distinguishing normal from active retinoblastoma and 0.992 accuracy for differentiating normal from active cases and 0.934 for differentiating stable and active retinoblastoma, demonstrating the superior representational capacity of residual networks, although its focus on a single tumor type limited broader generalization [11].

More recently, the UWF Fundus Images of Intraocular Tumors dataset introduced a multi-class benchmark comprising 2,031 images across six categories, including normal eyes and five intraocular tumor types (Retinal Capillary Hemangioma, Choroidal Osteoma, Uveal Melanoma, Retinoblastoma, Choroidal Hemangioma). Evaluation of multiple architectures, including ResNet-50, ResNet-101, ConvNeXt-T, and Vision Transformer (ViT-B), in this study demonstrated high specificity (>94%) across all models, with ViT-B achieving the highest overall performance (accuracy = 91.46%, AUC = 96.87%, F1-score = 81.42%, Kappa = 84.14%) [2]. These results highlight the feasibility of automated multi-class intraocular tumor classification and the potential of DL models, particularly CNN-based architectures, in handling complex ophthalmic imaging data.

Building upon these findings, the present study focuses on multi-class classification of intraocular tumors using an ultra-wide-field fundus image dataset. The present study aims to develop a robust multi-class classification framework for intraocular tumors, improving diagnostic coverage, facilitating early detection of diverse tumor types, and bridging the gap

between existing single-task studies and the clinical need for comprehensive automated diagnostic tools.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the present study, the "UWF Fundus Images of Intraocular Tumors" dataset, released on Figshare [22], was utilized. The dataset comprises 2,031 ultra-widefield (UWF) fundus images collected between 2019 and 2024 at Shenzhen Eye Hospital (SZEH) using the Optomap Daytona scanning laser ophthalmoscope (SLO), an ultra-widefield fundus imaging system.

Among these images, 677 depict intraocular tumors and 1,354 represent healthy controls, obtained from 332 eyes of 218 Asian individuals. For some eyes, multiple images were captured at different disease stages to document tumor progression or treatment response over time. The dataset comprises six classes: one normal class and five intraocular tumor classes, including Retinal Capillary Hemangioma (RCH), Choroidal Osteoma (CO), Uveal Melanoma (UM), Retinoblastoma (RB), and Choroidal Hemangioma (CH).

Figure 2: Representative UWF fundus images of six categories of the "UWF Fundus Images of Intraocular Tumors" dataset. (a) Normal fundus images, (b) Retinal Capillary Hemangioma (RCH), (c) Choroidal Osteoma (CO), (d) Uveal Melanoma (UM), (e) Retinoblastoma (RB), (f) Choroidal Hemangioma (CH) [2].

Table 1. Distribution of images in each class

Class Name	Total Image	Train	Validation	Test
Normal	1354	948	271	135
Choroidal Hemangioma (CH)	71	50	14	7
Choroidal Osteoma (CO)	80	56	16	8
Retinal Capillary Hemangioma (RCH)	186	130	37	19
Retinoblastoma (RB)	255	179	51	25
Uveal Melanoma (UM)	85	60	17	8

The distribution of images across these classes is presented in Table 1. The data were split into training, validation, and test subsets in a 7:2:1 ratio. To prevent images from the same patient appearing in different subsets and to prevent data leakage, the first 70% of images in each class were assigned to the training set, the next 20% to the validation set, and the remaining 10% to the test set.

In this study, we adopt ResNet-50 as the backbone convolutional neural network for multi-class classification of ultra-widefield fundus images. ResNet (Residual Network) is a deep convolutional architecture introduced by He et al. in 2015, designed to facilitate the training of very deep neural networks by addressing fundamental optimization challenges associated with increasing network depth [23].

This operation is implemented through shortcut (skip) connections that bypass one or more layers and directly add the input back to later layers. Such identity mappings enable gradients to propagate more effectively during backpropagation and mitigate problems associated with vanishing gradients, thus allowing for substantially deeper architectures to be trained end-to-end.

ResNet-50 specifically refers to a 50-layer residual network that employs a bottleneck architecture, where each residual block contains a sequence of 1×1 , 3×3 , and 1×1 convolutional layers. These blocks reduce computational cost while retaining representational capacity, making ResNet-50 a widely adopted model in medical image analysis and transfer learning applications.

To further enhance feature representation, we incorporated Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) attention blocks into the residual network. The SE block, introduced by Hu et al. in 2018, adaptively recalibrates channel-wise feature responses by explicitly modelling interdependencies between channels. This is achieved through a squeeze operation, which

performs global average pooling to capture channel-wise statistics, followed by an excitation operation, consisting of two fully connected layers with non-linearities and a sigmoid activation to generate channel-wise weights. These weights are then used to scale the original feature maps, emphasizing informative features while suppressing less relevant ones [24].

In our implementation, we evaluated the impact of adding SE blocks to different stages (layer1–layer4) of ResNet-50, corresponding to the four main residual stages in the network. This allowed us to systematically investigate how attention at different depths affects classification performance for intraocular tumor detection. By integrating SE attention, the network is able to focus more selectively on diagnostically relevant structures within fundus images, improving its ability to capture subtle pathological variations without significantly increasing computational complexity.

In addition, we examined the effect of freezing the early residual layers during training. Freezing initial layers allows the network to preserve low-level feature representations learned from pretraining on large-scale datasets (e.g., ImageNet), while only updating higher-level layers to adapt to domain-specific intraocular tumor patterns. This approach reduces overfitting on relatively small medical datasets and can accelerate convergence, but may limit the model’s ability to adapt fully to unique characteristics of ultra-widefield fundus images. By systematically varying the number of frozen layers, we assessed how retaining pre-trained low-level features versus fine-tuning deeper layers influences classification accuracy and overall model robustness.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, we systematically evaluated the performance of the ResNet-50 model on ultra-widefield fundus images to identify an optimal architecture and achieve accurate classification of intraocular tumors.

1-4- Evaluation of input resolution

To evaluate the impact of input resolution on model performance, experiments were performed using 224, 640, and 768 pixel inputs. The original ultra-widefield fundus images possess very high spatial resolution (3000–4000 pixels), enabling the capture of fine pathological details. However, directly processing full-resolution images is computationally prohibitive.

Our results indicate that a resolution of 768 provides the most favorable trade-off between preserving diagnostically relevant fine-grained features and maintaining computational feasibility. At this resolution, subtle tumor boundaries, vascular patterns, and texture variations remain sufficiently represented. Lower resolutions, such as 224, involve substantial down sampling, which may lead to partial loss of spatial information, as reflected by slightly lower F1-score and Cohen’s Kappa on the test set. Conversely, resolutions higher than 768 yield marginal performance improvements while significantly increasing GPU memory consumption and training time. Therefore, 768 was selected as the baseline resolution for subsequent architectural ablation experiments.

Table 2 .The effect of input image resolution on classification accuracy

Image input resolution for resnet50	Validation				Test			
	Accuracy	Precision	F1-score	Cohen Kappa	Accuracy	Precision	F1-score	Cohen Kappa
224	0.955	0.957	0.953	0.913	0.930	0.934	0.916	0.862
640	0.933	0.938	0.928	0.866	0.955	0.949	0.947	0.912
768	0.936	0.938	0.931	0.871	0.965	0.958	0.957	0.931

2-4- Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) attention

Using 768 as the fixed input resolution, we further investigated the impact of integrating Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) attention into different residual stages of ResNet-50. ResNet-50 consists of four main residual stages (layer1–layer4), each responsible for progressively higher-level feature abstraction. To analyze the contribution of attention at different depths, we compared the following configurations:

- Baseline ResNet-50 (without attention)
- SE added only to layer 4
- SE added to layers 3 and 4
- SE added to layers 1, 2, 3, and 4

This design enables systematic evaluation of shallow versus deep attention integration. Since early layers capture low-level features (edges, color gradients), while deeper layers encode more semantic and task-specific representations, inserting attention at different stages may affect performance differently. In particular, attention in deeper layers is expected to enhance tumor-specific feature discrimination, whereas attention in earlier layers may introduce additional parameters without substantial semantic benefit.

All models were trained under identical optimization settings to ensure a fair comparison. Specifically, training was conducted for 50 epochs with a batch size of 8, using stochastic gradient descent with an initial learning rate of 0.001 and a final learning rate factor of 0.01 under a cosine decay schedule. A momentum coefficient of 0.937 and weight decay of 3×10^{-4} were applied for regularization, and a three-epoch warm-up strategy was employed to stabilize early training dynamics.

In addition to architectural modifications, special consideration was given to the class imbalance present in the dataset. As shown in Table 1, the distribution of samples across categories is highly skewed, with the normal class substantially outnumbering several tumor classes (e.g., CH, CO, and UM). Such imbalance can bias the learning process toward

majority classes, leading to degraded sensitivity for minority tumor categories. To mitigate this issue, class-weighted cross-entropy loss was employed during training. The weights were assigned inversely proportional to class frequencies, ensuring that misclassification of underrepresented tumor classes incurred a higher penalty.

The introduction of class weighting proved to be a critical factor in improving the discriminative performance of the ResNet-50 model. In particular, it enhanced Accuracy and F1-score for minority tumor classes, contributing significantly to the overall increase in test accuracy and Cohen’s Kappa. These findings indicate that performance gains were not solely attributable to attention mechanisms, but were strongly influenced by addressing dataset imbalance through appropriate loss re-weighting.

Furthermore, basic data augmentation techniques were applied to improve generalization and reduce overfitting. These included random horizontal and vertical flipping, small-angle random rotations, brightness variations, and input normalization. Such transformations increase the effective diversity of training samples while preserving clinically relevant tumor characteristics. The use of augmentation was particularly beneficial given the limited size of several tumor categories, allowing the model to learn more invariant and robust feature representations.

All models were optimized using stochastic gradient descent (SGD), which demonstrated stable convergence and strong generalization performance in our experiments. Compared to adaptive optimizers, SGD with momentum provided more consistent validation-to-test behavior, particularly when combined with class weighting and controlled regularization. Collectively, the integration of class-balanced loss, data augmentation, and SGD optimization contributed substantially to the observed improvements in classification accuracy and robustness.

Table 3. The result of adding attention blocks in different layers of ResNet50 on the model’s performance

Model	Validation				Test			
	Accuracy	Precision	F1-score	Cohen Kappa	Accuracy	Precision	F1-score	Cohen Kappa
Baseline ResNet-50	0.936	0.936	0.933	0.875	0.975	0.977	0.974	0.952
SE added to layer 4	0.928	0.940	0.927	0.862	0.985	0.989	0.986	0.972
SE added to layers 3 and 4	0.948	0.957	0.94	0.901	0.950	0.968	0.955	0.910
SE added to layers 1, 2, 3, and 4	0.968	0.970	0.967	0.939	0.960	0.961	0.960	0.925

Table 3 presents a comparative evaluation of different attention integration strategies within ResNet-50 for intraocular tumor classification. The baseline ResNet-50 already demonstrates strong generalization performance (Test Accuracy = 0.975, F1-score = 0.974, Kappa = 0.952), indicating that transfer learning with deep residual representations is highly effective for ultra-widefield fundus images. It is important to note that this strong baseline performance was achieved not only due to the representational capacity of ResNet-50, but also as a result of incorporating class-weighted loss to address dataset imbalance.

3-4- Layer Freezing

To further optimize generalization and control model complexity, we investigated the effect of freezing early convolutional layers of ResNet-50 during fine-tuning. In transfer learning settings, the initial residual blocks typically capture low-level visual primitives such as edges, intensity gradients, and basic texture patterns, which are often transferable across natural and medical image domains. Freezing these layers can preserve pretrained representations while reducing the number of trainable parameters, mitigating overfitting—particularly in relatively limited medical datasets.

Table 4. The result of layer freezing on the ResNet50 classification model performance.

Model	Validation				Test			
	Accuracy	Precision	F1-score	Cohen Kappa	Accuracy	Precision	F1-score	Cohen Kappa
Baseline ResNet-50	0.936	0.936	0.933	0.875	0.975	0.977	0.974	0.952
Layer 1 and 2 froze	0.945	0.947	0.944	0.895	0.955	0.954	0.953	0.914
Layer 1, 2 and 3 froze	0.933	0.936	0.932	0.873	0.965	0.966	0.963	0.933

The experiments on layer freezing indicate that selectively constraining early convolutional layers in ResNet50 can influence both model generalization and robustness. Freezing layers 1 and 2 slightly improved validation performance compared to the baseline, suggesting that retaining pretrained low-level features stabilizes learning and mitigates overfitting. However, this configuration led to a modest decrease in test performance, indicating limited adaptation to unseen tumor-specific patterns.

Freezing layers 1 to 3, in contrast, reduced validation metrics slightly but improved test set performance relative to freezing only the first two layers, demonstrating enhanced generalization on unseen data. These results imply a trade-off: freezing early layers preserves transferable low-level representations while allowing deeper layers to learn task-specific features. Overall, the findings suggest that strategic freezing of initial residual blocks serves

as an effective regularization mechanism, improving robustness in multi-class intraocular tumor classification, particularly under limited dataset conditions

4-4- Combined Effect of Attention and Layer Freezing

Following the independent evaluation of Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) attention and layer freezing strategies, we further investigated the combined effect of these two regularization mechanisms within ResNet-50. While deep-stage SE integration (particularly in layer 4) demonstrated improved discriminative capability, and freezing early residual blocks aimed to preserve transferable low-level representations, their joint application may provide a complementary balance between feature refinement and parameter stability.

In this configuration, SE blocks were integrated into the deepest residual stage while the initial convolutional and early residual layers were frozen during fine-tuning. This design allows the network to retain stable low-level visual descriptors—such as edges, vascular contours, and intensity gradients- while selectively enhancing high-level tumor-specific semantic representations through channel-wise attention. Simultaneously, reducing the number of trainable parameters may limit overfitting and improve robustness on unseen test data.

Table 5. Combined Effect of Attention and Layer Freezing on the ResNet50 Classification Model Performance

Model	Params	FLOPs	Validation				Test			
			Accuracy	Precision	F1-score	Cohen Kappa	Accuracy	Precision	F1-score	Cohen Kappa
Baseline ResNet-50	23.52M	48.57G	0.936	0.936	0.933	0.875	0.975	0.977	0.974	0.952
Freeze L1–2, SE L4	25.09M	48.57G	0.945	0.952	0.946	0.8967	0.970	0.975	0.969	0.943
Freeze L1–2, SE L3–4	25.88M	48.59G	0.960	0.963	0.960	0.925	0.930	0.944	0.935	0.872
Freeze L1–2, SE L1–4	26.04M	48.64G	0.958	0.961	0.958	0.921	0.960	0.965	0.961	0.925

The combined evaluation of Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) attention and early layer freezing demonstrates a nuanced impact on model performance. Integrating SE blocks into the deepest residual stage (layer 4) while freezing layers 1 and 2 led to a notable improvement in validation metrics compared to the baseline, with Accuracy = 0.945 and F1-score = 0.946, indicating enhanced feature discrimination and reduced overfitting. Test set performance remained high (Accuracy = 0.970, F1-score = 0.969), confirming that selective attention in deep layers, coupled with retention of pretrained low-level features, preserves generalization capability.

Expanding SE integration to layers 3 and 4, while still freezing layers 1 and 2, further increased validation metrics (Accuracy = 0.960, F1-score = 0.960); however, test set performance declined (Accuracy = 0.930, F1-score = 0.935), suggesting overfitting to the training data due to increased model complexity. Similarly, applying SE across all layers (1–4) achieved high validation scores but led to reduced test performance (Accuracy = 0.960, F1-score = 0.961), reinforcing that attention in early layers provides limited discriminative benefit and may destabilize generalization.

These results highlight that selective integration of attention into the deepest residual layers, combined with freezing initial layers, provides an optimal trade-off between feature refinement and parameter stability. This configuration improves intraocular tumor classification by enhancing high-level semantic representations while retaining stable low-level descriptors, and it is particularly effective for limited datasets where overfitting is a concern. Overall, the findings emphasize that careful design of attention placement and layer freezing strategies is critical for achieving robust multi-class classification performance in medical imaging tasks.

6. Discussion

This study systematically investigated architectural and optimization strategies for multi-class classification of intraocular tumors in ultra-widefield fundus images using a ResNet-50 backbone. Through structured ablation experiments, we evaluated the influence of input resolution, Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) attention placement, layer freezing, and training strategies on model robustness and generalization.

The findings confirm that preserving higher spatial resolution (768×768) is essential for maintaining diagnostically relevant fine-grained features while remaining computationally feasible. More critically, the depth of attention integration significantly influences model behavior. Selective incorporation of SE blocks exclusively in the deepest residual stage (layer 4) achieved the highest test performance (Accuracy = 0.985, F1-score = 0.986, Cohen's Kappa = 0.972), outperforming both the baseline model and configurations with broader attention distribution. In contrast, extending attention to intermediate or shallow layers increased model complexity without yielding consistent improvements in generalization, and in some cases led to reduced robustness on unseen data.

Beyond architectural design, optimization strategies played a pivotal role in achieving high performance. Given the pronounced class imbalance in the dataset, the adoption of class-weighted loss was a critical factor in improving model fairness and sensitivity across minority tumor categories. By penalizing misclassification of underrepresented classes more strongly, class weighting substantially enhanced recall and F1-score, contributing significantly to the overall increase in test accuracy and Cohen's Kappa.

Additionally, the application of basic yet effective data augmentation techniques including random flipping, rotation, brightness adjustment, and normalization, improved generalization by increasing the effective diversity of the training data. These augmentations were particularly important for mitigating overfitting in tumor classes with limited samples.

Combined with the use of stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimization, which demonstrated stable convergence and consistent validation-to-test behavior, these training strategies significantly strengthened the robustness of the model.

Layer freezing experiments further demonstrated that constraining early residual blocks can function as an effective regularization mechanism under limited dataset conditions. However, excessive freezing may restrict domain-specific adaptation. When combining freezing with selective deep-stage attention, stable and competitive results were achieved, though this configuration did not surpass the performance of the model using SE exclusively in the deepest residual stage without additional freezing.

7. Conclusion

Overall, the experimental evidence indicates that optimal performance is achieved not merely through architectural enhancement, but through a carefully balanced integration of resolution selection, selective attention placement, class-balanced optimization, data augmentation, and stable SGD-based optimization. In particular, class-weighted loss and simple yet effective augmentation strategies played a substantial role in improving robustness under dataset imbalance. ResNet-50 with SE attention integrated solely in layer 4 at an input resolution of 768×768 pixels, combined with class-weighted training and augmentation, achieved the best test performance (Accuracy = 0.985, F1-score = 0.986, Cohen's Kappa = 0.972). The proposed framework therefore provides a robust and clinically promising solution for automated multi-class intraocular tumor classification in ultra-widefield fundus imaging.

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